

The Creative Metacognition in AI Generation (CMC-AI) Scale

Instruction to participants: Please rate the extent to which you agree with the following statements regarding your use of Generative AI in design tasks (1 = Strongly Disagree, 7 = Strongly Agree).

Dimension	Item Code	Item Content
Iterative Resilience	Q1	I spend a long time debugging or regenerating prompts until the output matches my vision.
	Q2	I constantly adjust parameters (e.g., weights, styles) until I am satisfied with the result.
	Q3	I proactively explore AI techniques beyond the immediate requirements of the homework.
	Q4	I frequently use in-painting or local repainting features to fix specific details.
	Q5	I spend significant time finding high-quality reference images to guide the AI generation.
	Q6	I use professional standards (e.g., anatomy, perspective) to screen the AI outputs rigorously.
AI Anxiety & Efficacy	Q7 (R)	I prefer using simple or colloquial prompts rather than complex professional terms.
	Q8 (R)	I cannot explain exactly how the final output was generated by the AI.
	Q9 (R)	I often feel that learning manual design skills is becoming futile.
	Q10 (R)	I worry that I am losing my independent creation ability due to reliance on AI.
Agency Maintenance	Q11	I use professional design terminology (e.g., lighting, composition) to control the AI generation.
	Q12	I can fluently explain the design logic behind the AI-generated images.
	Q13	I can justify why I selected a specific output from multiple generated options.
	Q14	I can articulate the evolution process of my creative idea throughout the AI interaction.
	Q15	I firmly believe that AI is just a tool and I remain the primary author of the design.

Note. (R) indicates reverse-coded items.